

Can the Jonckheere trend test be recommended to evaluate genetic association studies?

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Abstract

In a recent paper by Manning et al. entitled *A nonparametric alternative to the Cochran-Armitage trend test in genetic case-control association studies: The Jonckheere-Terpstra trend test*, the Jonckheere trend test was recommended for case-control studies in genetic association studies. This proposal is critically questioned here. Instead, maximum tests over the three mode of inheritances: additive, recessive and dominant are proposed: i) for case-control studies the max-test for multiple contrasts according [4], ii) for studies with approximately Gaussian distributed traits the max-test based on regression models [8] using the multiple marginal models approach [6] and iii) for non-normal traits the non-parametric multiple contrast test [10] can be recommended.

1 Introduction

A recent paper [11], entitled *'A nonparametric alternative to the Cochran-Armitage trend test in genetic case-control association studies: The Jonckheere-Terpstra trend test'*, recommended for the analysis of genetic case-control association studies *'JT trend test outperforms the CA trend test across the spectrum of genetic models'*. The common used Cochran-Armitage trend test [1] is test on the slope of a linear regression for weighted proportions in 2-by-k table data. I.e. this test is most powerful when the alternative is linear, i.e. the additive mode of inheritance. For the possible modes recessive and dominant, the power is consequently lower. Alternatives are maximum tests across these 3 models: either formulated as multiple contrast tests assuming a qualitative factor with levels aa, aA, AA [4] or regression models assuming a quantitative covariate with equidistant scores (0,1,2) [8]. The search for a simple 'super test' that is sensitive to these various ordered alternatives is certainly interesting - but is it the JT test?

2 The Jonckheere trend test

The Jonckheere trend test [7] is a nonparametric test for ordered alternative using pairwise Wilcoxon-type ranks defined for continuous data. In genetic association studies commonly a oneway-layout is considered with $k = 3$ treatment groups. In case control studies, 2-by-k table data occur, i.e. proportions are considered. Moreover, the tables can be outcome-specific rather unbalanced, e.g. $n_{CC} = 158, n_{CT} = 150, n_{TT} = 25$ in the association between psoriasis and the IL1B511 locus [13]. The JT test is powerful for near-to-linear alternatives [12]. Notice, for $k=3$, the JT test based on the sum of specific Wilcoxon scores $U_{12} + U_{23} + 2 * U_{13}$, i.e. for the levels aa, aA, AA: $U_{aa,aA} + U_{aA,AA} + 2 * U_{aa,AA}$ and therefore sensitive to all three models. JT test can be used for proportions only approximately for large sample

sizes which is an uncommon approach. A more appropriate test based on the relative effect size which is defined for discrete data as well. A related order restricted test [9] and a maximum test for association studies are available [10].

Because JT test is defined for continuous data, a simulation study using just Gaussian distributed data is used to compare with a linear regression model (as an analog to Armitage trend test), a maximum multiple contrast test and the Tukey trend test, a maximum test over the arithmetic, ordinal and logarithmic dose scores [14].

Notice, the CA-test based on the assumption of a regression model with fixed levels (model I), i.e. a-priori randomized levels of a continuous covariable. This is not the case in genetic association case-control studies.

3 A tiny simulation study

Normal distributed variables with homoscedastic and heteroscedastic errors were generated and the size under H_0 and the power under the three genetic models were estimated for small samples sizes $N = 60$ and equidistant dose scores $D = 0, 1, 2$ (5000 runs).

Hypo	Design	Variance	Tukey	lin Reg	JT	MAX
H_0	balanced	homo	0.049	0.052	0.043	0.050
		hetero	0.082	0.093	0.070	0.076
	unbalanced	homo	0.048	0.044	0.048	0.049
		hetero	0.120	0.158	0.079	0.140
additive	balanced	homo	0.949	0.900	0.934	0.925
		hetero	0.625	0.516	0.634	0.548
dominant		homo	0.934	0.873	0.915	0.968
		hetero	0.609	0.502	0.520	0.615
recessive		homo	0.933	0.875	0.911	0.970
		hetero	0.603	0.491	0.689	0.660
additive	unbalanced	homo	0.897	0.825	0.875	0.869
		hetero	0.655	0.564	0.647	0.614
dominant		homo	0.722	0.590	0.558	0.875
		hetero	0.511	0.416	0.287	0.588
recessive		homo	0.960	0.918	0.971	0.967
		hetero	0.726	0.648	0.861	0.763

Table 1: Power and size for additive, recessive and dominant model for small n_i in $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$

All power estimates for the heteroscedastic case are biased due to inflationary size under H_0 (see Table 2). I.e. all power estimates for heterogeneous variances are uncertain in this Table. For homogeneous variances, the JT test reveals the highest power only in the case of the recessive mode in unbalanced design, not surprising because of the definition of its test statistics. In all other scenarios, either the Max test or the Tukey-type test reveal the highest power. And this power advantage varies from small values to remarkable difference in the dominant mode: $\pi = 0.88$ for the Max test, but only $\pi = 0.56$ for the JT test.

4 The effect of heteroscedasticity

Both unbalancedness, caused by data-dependent chance and not by a priori design, and heteroscedasticity are common in genetic association studies [5]. Therefore, a modification of the above tests should be considered: replacing the common means square error estimator by the sandwich estimator [3],[6]. In the next simulation study the sandwich-Tukey, sandwich-Max are compared with the JT test and the nonparametric test for relative effect size, known to be robust against heteroscedasticity,

Not surprising, that both JT and regression tests reveal small power for the dominant mode because of $\mu_{aa} < \mu_{aA} = \mu_{AA}$ with the risk allele aa . On the other hand the power of the recessive mode is similar to the additive model because $\mu_{aa} = \mu_{aA} < \mu_{AA}$ whereas in the $k = 3$ design the scores for additive mode is $-1, 0, 1$, i.e. the allele aA is ignored.

Hypo	Design	Variance	sand-Tu	JT	sand-MAX	KO
H_0	balanced	homo	0.053	0.046	0.058	0.049
	balanced	hetero	0.055	0.069	0.058	0.048
	unbalanced	homo	0.055	0.050	0.064	0.048
	unbalanced	hetero	0.067	0.073	0.073	0.049
dominant	balanced	homo	0.812	0.781	0.860	0.834
recessive	balanced	homo	0.811	0.778	0.861	0.836
additive	balanced	homo	0.817	0.784	0.791	0.757
dominant	balanced	hetero	0.489	0.453	0.493	0.407
recessive	balanced	hetero	0.501	0.614	0.706	0.690
additive	balanced	hetero	0.489	0.542	0.526	0.466
dominant	unbalanced	homo	0.550	0.437	0.710	0.628
recessive	unbalanced	homo	0.844	0.857	0.856	0.796
additive	unbalanced	homo	0.729	0.686	0.706	0.623
dominant	unbalanced	hetero	0.314	0.265	0.348	0.255
recessive	unbalanced	hetero	0.540	0.752	0.611	0.571
additive	unbalanced	hetero	0.442	0.530	0.439	0.357

Table 2: Power and size for sandwich modified tests in comparison with JT test for small n_i in $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$

Notice, only for small sample sizes, the sandwich modifications reveals inflationary size for MAX test, see [2]. The nonparametric KO test reveals similar, superior or inferior power to the JT-test, but controls the size under variance heteroscedasticity in unbalanced designs.

5 The problems with stand-alone tests

Both the CA test and the JT test are stand-alone formulations, i.e. they are designed precisely for an one-way design and an exact data situation. In genetic association studies however, covariates should be included in the model and extensions such as mixed effect model, e.g. for several studies should be available. Both TU-test and MAX-test belong to this more general class of generalized linear mixed effect models.

6 Summary

First of all, it is not obvious to use the JT test for proportions in case-control studies, because it is defined for continuous data. Still, proportion can be analysed for very large sample sizes. Case-control studies

in medicine in particular show rather low sample sizes, especially in the risk allele group, where only $n_{aa} = 5$ cases may be recorded only. Such scenarios were investigated in a simulation study using normal distributed data.

A recommendation of the JT test cannot be concluded from this.

Instead, maximum-tests are recommended: for case-control studies the max-test for multiple contrasts according [4], for studies with approximately Gaussian distributed traits the max-test based on regression models [8] using the multiple marginal models approach [6] as well as the non-parametric multiple contrast test [10] for non-normal traits can be recommended. CRAN R packages are available for these three tests.

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